

Phylogenetic signal in the lexicon: Are parental terms influenced by baby talk?

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Work in progress

CROSS-LANGUAGE PARALLELS IN PARENTAL KIN TERMS

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Innumerable anthropologists and linguists have asserted a universal tendency for languages, regardless of their historical relationships, to develop similar words for father and mother on the basis of nursery forms. As standard parental terms become phonetically and morphologically modified in consequence of the normal processes of linguistic change, forms develop which are difficult for very young children to pronounce. Under such circumstances, simpler nursery words tend to appear — carved, so to speak, out of infant babblings under parental encouragement. From time to time, it is alleged, such nursery forms come to replace the traditional words in standard usage. Since their phonetic range is severely limited by the speech potentialities of young children, similar forms tend to crop up through convergence in historically unrelated languages.

“Mama” / “Papa”: Stable Words or Baby Talk?

- Case study of phylogenetic signal and evolution of terms for parents (i.e. ‘mother’ and ‘father’)
- Quantitative evaluation of claims
- “mama/papa/dada” and their effect on reference terms
 - cf. Jakobson 1962, Murdock 1959

Parental Terms:

- universally lexicalized
- acquired early
- tend to contain phonologically stable segments (e.g. fewer affricates, ejectives, etc)

< more phyl'ic signal

- influenced by baby talk phonology
- replaced by baby talk forms
- address vs reference forms
- register variation

more random variation>

Today: Aims

- Illustration of quantitative approach to old question in historical linguistics
- Contribution to understanding evolution of lexicon [small slice!]
- Investigating how arbitrary non-arbitrary can be

- Better understanding relationships between constraints on lexical transmission and phylogenetic signal
- Case study of ‘process’ in micro and its outcomes in macro-change

Data and Methods

3 phylogenies

- Pama-Nyungan [243 langs]
 - Austronesian [369 langs]
 - Indo-European [100 langs]
- Translation equivalents for 'mother' and 'father'
 - c 700 languages in sample
 - families represent c. 30% of the world's languages

Coding

- 2 meaning classes ('mother' and 'father')
- Each cognate coded as 'state'
- States converted to binary characters (presence/absence of form X in meaning Y)

'mother'	* η ama		* η apaŋ		* η aŋka	
Djinang	ama	1		0		0
Kungardutyi	η ama	1		0		0
Batyala		0	η avaŋ	1		0
Waka-Kabi		0	η apaŋ	1		0
Panyjima		0		0	η aŋka	1
Kurrama		0		0	η aŋka	1
Martuthunira		0		0	η aŋka	1

Methods: suite of investigation

1. **PCA (Principle components analysis)** - mother/father in the context of basic vocabulary: which meaning classes behave like each other in the data? Are mother/father like each other? Like 'high cognacy' or 'low cognacy' meanings? [Pama-Nyungan only]
2. **Phylogenetic signal**: D-statistics and measuring conservatism/phylogenetic signal [All families]
3. **Phonology**: Apicals and Labials: do words with 'baby talk' features (e.g. reduplication) behave differently from words with other consonants? Are words with baby talk consonants disproportionately frequent in parental terms? Do such words show different characteristics? [All families]

***D* statistic**

Selectivity in Mammalian Extinction Risk and Threat Types: a New Measure of Phylogenetic Signal Strength in Binary Traits

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- sister languages & sister nodes within the tree
- **observed** distinctness from one another
- vs **expected** distinctness for evolution under Brownian motion
- compared against two null hypotheses:
 - Brownian evolution – random evolution down tree
 - un-tree-like randomness – random distribution along tips

D statistic

D Statistic

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Results

PCA

PCA

- Max.class.size: number of langs in largest cog set [measure of retention]
 - Number of singletons/number of cog classes per meaning: [measure of innovation]
 - Missing: [utility for phylogenetic comparison]
-
- Mother/father are similar
 - Mother/father are conservative, but not the most conservative

Phylogenetic Signal

Proliferation of Terms

Number of forms

- IE and Aus'n have terms that dominate; PNY doesn't

Cognate class size as percentage of languages in family

Mother

Father

Phylogenetic Signal

(D statistics)

Any significant differences between families?

- No.
- (linear regression with family, term, and their interaction as variables)
- [Only significant difference is between terms]

Compared to other vocabulary? [PNy only]

- All parts of speech show variation (borrowing, inheritance, etc)
- Means all similar
- Mother/Father DStats show same type of range.

Phonology

Are D statistics higher for baby-talk forms?

Labials

Apicals

Reduplicated Terms

- Higher average D statistic
- But not a significant difference

Are baby-talk consonants disproportionately frequent in parental terms?

- Chi-Square test [test of fit between observed and expected distributions of segments to test for interactions between variables]

	Reduplicated	Not.Reduplicated
Parental.Term	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>
Not.Parental	<i>c</i>	<i>d</i>

- Tested for Pama-Nyungan only, against other kin terms [MM, MF, B, Z, BW, MB, FZ, ZH]

Disproportionate baby-talk forms?

	Redup	Labial	Apical	Palatal
Parents	×	×	✓	×
G'parents	✓	×	×	×
Siblings	×	×	×	×

Conclusions

Conclusions

- Findings:
 - Terms show phylogenetic signal.
 - The “baby talk” terms show less.
 - But not significantly so.
- The results are consistent across language families, though the terms are less conservative in Pama-Nyungan.
- There is probably an effect of child acquisition, but not enough to swamp regular transmission.

Thank you!

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